

BIOFILM FORMATION BY *PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA* AND *METHICILLIN RESISTANT STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* (MRSA) VIA TISSUE CULTURE AND TUBE METHODS IN COMBINATION WITH DIFFERENT ANTIBIOTICS BY USING PLANT CELLS

Aqeel Abbas Kareem

Department of clinically and Laboratory Science- College of Pharmacy-University of AL-Qadisiyah-Iraq

Abstract: Objective: This project designed to determine the effect of Plant cells extract in combined with conventional antibiotics against two multidrug biofilm forming pathogens and was conducted to compare two methods for the detection of biofilms role.

Methods: This study was conducted previously at a period from December 2018-to October 2019. Conventional cultural and biochemical methods were employed to isolate and identify biofilm-producing bacteria from clinical specimens. Standard strains of bacteria were also employed. Eating mushrooms as a bio-reductant helped to create silver nanoparticles. By employing an electronic microscope, a UV/visual spectrophotometer, and an extract color that changed from clear yellow to brown, Ag-Nps' biosynthesis was demonstrated. Then, using the diffusion method in conjunction with antibiotics, Ag-Nps was experienced compared to bacterial strains and biofilm-producing bacteria.

Results: The biosynthesized Ag-Nps were assessed using the circle distribution approach alongside Methicillin-Resistant Staph aureus and Pseudomonas aeruginosa. On the other hand, those assessments of the combined impact stayed extended (5-50 nm) in scope and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) in peak 430 cm⁻¹ denotes to proteins creation dot. The combined effect of Ag-Nps and antibiotic resistance was observed in the results.

Conclusion: The mixture of nanoparticles and antibiotics reserved the capability to formula biofilm more effectively than the use of antibiotics only, suggesting that Ag-NPs have bigger possible as antimicrobial mixes alongside biofilm creation. This suggests that Ag-NPs may be used to treat infectious diseases, as Ag-NPs and antibiotics have the highest antibacterial activity.

Keywords: Ag-NPs; (Mushroom); pseudomonas, (MRSA); Antibiotics.

Introduction

Microorganisms with the ability to form biofilms include both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Staphylococcus aureus are two of the frequently implicated bacteria. (1) There are several ways to identify the formation of biofilms. These include fluorescent microscopic inspection, piezoelectric sensors, bioluminescent assay, Tissue Culture Plate (TCP), Tube technique (TM), and Congo Red Agar technique (CRA). Assess for TCP biofilms. Global reports of multidrug-resistant organisms have led to their recognition as one of the hardest infections linked to healthcare settings to manage and cure(2). The study of microbial biofilm has drawn a lot of attention in recent decades As a result, research and

techniques for diagnosing virulent bacterial strains, i. e. strains that are capable of producing slime. In order to improve patient care and develop effective strategies for biofilm control, subsequent biofilm formations are required(3). Fifty clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were used in the detection of biofilm formation techniques(4). We identified the clinical isolates using standard microbiological protocol. Biofilm-producing bacteria stayed exposed to an antibiotic susceptibility exam by means of the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion process. The Tube method (TM) was used to test for biofilm, while the TCP method used broth media supplemented with 1 percent sucrose.. Both methods require the use of solid media, specifically brain heart infusion broth. Of the 50 isolates, the TCP method identified 8 and 5 as high biofilm producers, while the TM method identified 7 and 10 as isolates with strong biofilm formation and no biofilm produced for *P. aeruginosa* S.. *aureus* were 15 and 5, respectively, weak. The results of the antibiotic susceptibility test showed that bacteria that produced biofilms had higher levels of antibiotic resistance than bacteria that did not. Thus, the results of this investigation indicate that the TCP technique is repeatable and profound. TM technique produced mediocre outcomes. Therefore, when compared to the other method used in this investigation, the TCP method is more appropriate for the detection of biofilm formation.(5,6,).

Materials and Method

Selection of Isolates: This study was conducted previously at a period from December 2018-to October 2019. In AL-Diywaniyah Province –Iraq-University of AL-Qadysiah

Biofilm detection method was applied to 50 clinical isolates in total. Samples were taken from ear samples, few pus specimens, tips of intravenous catheters, and urinary catheter tips, among other places. The complete collection was obtained from hospitalized patients who had nosocomial infections. Using standard microbiological techniques, isolates were identified (Gram staining, cultural characteristics, catalase test, Oxidase test, biochemical test(7).

Grounding of Crude Extract of Edible Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*)

Edible *Agaricus bisporus* (white button) mushrooms that stood obtained as of marketable foundations were used to create the Ag-NPs. 20 grams or so. of the mushroom was measured, then thoroughly cleaned using double-distilled water. After that, they were crushed and put in a beaker with 80 milliliters of distilled water that was sterile. After agitating the mixture for roughly two hours, Whatt man No. is used to filter it. One filter paper. Ag+ is biologically reduced to Ag⁰. The extract can be kept in a refrigerator at 4° C to be used in future studies (8).

Representation of Ag-NPs

Optical recognition and UV-Visible Spectroscopy

Ag-NP production expending *Agaricus bisporus* remove stayed demonstrated by a 24-hour color shift from yellow to dark brown. Additionally, UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-1600-PC Shimadzu) has been used to characterize it. Utilizing UV-Visible spectra by a resolve of 2.0 nm, the reaction between AgNO₃ and mushroom extract was observed between 200 and 700 nm (9, 10) with a peak at 430 nm (9,10).

Figure (1): 4:A peak (430 nm) measured by UV/Vis spectroscopy of silver nanoparticles produced by *Agaricus bisporus* after 1-3 days of incubation.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

At Al-Kuffa University College of Science / Center of Scientific Research, the size and shape of the biosynthesized Ag-NPs were analyzed using a scanning electron microscope. The silver nanoparticles with a dark brown color were extracted, cleaned, and at 10,000 g centrifugation for 20 minutes (11).

Figure (3): Agaricus bisporus in Iraq using scanning electron microscopy to analyze AgNPs.

Measurements using Fourier transmission infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy.

After the reaction, the leftover Ag-NPs solution from the Agaricus bisporus remove stayed detached at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes in order to eliminate any unwanted impurities. The supernatant was then centrifuged ten times for 15 minutes in order to repeat the solution. To obtain pure Ag-NPs, the pellets were rinsed with deionized water. The material was allowed to air dry completely at room temperature, and the resulting processed Ag-NPs were transported to F. T. I. R investigation between 250 and 4250 cm⁻¹.(12)

Figure (4): FTIR spectra of Agaricus bisporus in Iraq produced Ag-NPs.

➤ Antibacterial Action of Ag-NPs

Using Agaricus bisporus remove, the antibacterial action of Ag-NPs stood assessed using the agar disc diffusion technique (8). the optimal volume and concentration of Ag-NPs, various concentrations, and volumes were examined expending the agar disc diffusion technique. After loading agar wells through 20μL, 30μL, and 50μL of Ag-NPs suspension, Ag-NPs was added. The plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The dishes stood examined for regions of reticence following incubation. The increase in folded area was used to evaluate the activity.

➤ Antibacterial action and Ag-NPs

As stated by CLSI (2016) (12), the disc diffusion process stayed worked to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the antibiotics. Disc diffusion was used to combine Ag-NPs with antibiotics to combat bacterial isolates. Penicillin G, ampicillin, cefotaxime, gentamycin, and rifampicin are examples of antibiotics that block bacterial resistance. Ag-NPs were freshly prepared and impregnated onto discs, which were subsequently used for antibacterial activity assays to regulate the synergistic outcome of Ag-NPs (13). The region of

reticence for antibiotic and antibiotic by Ag-NPs, separately, is represented by A and B in the formula $(B2--A2)/A2$, which is used to measure antibacterial activity (14).

Biofilm Recognition Approaches:

A) To detect biofilm, the following techniques were used.

B) Tube method (TM)

This approach to biofilm detection is qualitative. a loopful of test organisms inoculated in check tubes comprising 10 ml of Trypticase soy broth comprising 1% glucose. For a full day, incubate the tubes at 37 °C. The tubes stayed poured, cleaned through phosphate buffer saline (pH 7.3), and desiccated after the incubation period. After that, tubes were discolored by 0.1 percent crystal violet. Clean any leftover dye with purified water. The tubes were dry with the ends facing down. The control strains' results were used to determine how to score the tube method. When a thick film was clearly visible lining the tube's wall and bottom, biofilm formation was deemed to be occurring(13).

B) - Tissue Culture Plate Method (TCP)

Fresh agar plate isolates stayed injected with 1 percent glucose (TSB glu) media on soya broth, allowed to incubate for 18 hours at 37 C, and then diluted 1 in 100 by fresh medium. To ensure sterility and non-specific media binding, 0 point 2 ml aliquots of the diluted cultures were placed into personal bores of sterile polystyrene in 96 well-flat bottom tissue culture dishes (Tarson Kolkata, India). Broth stayed utilized as a controlling. At 37°C, the tissue culture plates were incubated for 18 and 24 hours. Following incubation, each well's contents was carefully removed by tapping the plates. To get rid of "(14)planktonic" bacteria that float freely, the bores stood carefully washed three intervals using 0.2 mL of phosphate buffer saline (PBS pH 7.2). Using two percent sodium acetate as a fixative and zero percent crystal violet as a stain, the biofilm that adherent, "sessile" organisms created on the plate was stained. Plates were left to dry after the additional dye stayed thoroughly cleaned off through deionized water. Wells were consistently stained with crystal violet, and adherent cells typically form nano. Visual. At a wavelength of 570 nm, the density (OD) of stained adherent bacteria was measured using a micro ELISA auto reader (model PR 601, Qualigens). These OD values were considered as a quantity of the bacteria's capability to adhere to surfaces and formula biofilms. The average and subtraction of the OD readings as of the dye, fixative, and sterile medium stayed applied to all test values.(14)

➤ Antibiotic Susceptibility Check

The following antibiotic discs were used to test the antibiotic susceptibility of biofilm-producing bacteria: ampicillin, nalidixic acid, rifampicin, cloxacillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, oxcellin, and penicillin. Every antibiotic disc was utilized to combat strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*(15).

Result and Discussion

Twenty of the fifty isolates stayed Gram positive pathogens, and thirty stayed Gram negative. Among the Gram positive pathogens are *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Standard microbiological procedures were used to identify and characterize each of these isolates. These isolates were primarily obtained as of a diversity of medical samples, for instance blood, pus, sputum, urine, medical devices, and urinary catheter tips. Microbes that produce biofilms are mostly found in a specific region(16). Many stubborn infections are caused by bacteria that form biofilms, which are infamously hard to get rid of. They display antibiotic resistance in a number of ways, including limited antibiotic penetration into biofilm, slowed growth, and expression of resistance genes. Different techniques exist for detecting biofilms.(17,18,19,20) The ability of 50 isolates to form biofilm was assessed in this study using two different screening techniques. When paralleled to the Tube Technique (83 percent), the TCP process

produced a significant result of 90% strong biofilm production. Urine samples and urinary catheter tips are the primary sources of microbes that form biofilms. (Donlan, 2010).

(Table 1) Biofilm formation distribution using tube and tissue culture techniques.

Entire numeral of bacterial isolate	Biofilm creation	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		<i>S.aureus</i>	
		TCP	TM	TCP	TM
50	Strong	8	12	5	10
	Moderate	7	16	10	7
	Weak	15	2	5	3

Our findings concurred with those of Hassan et al. (2011) from Pakistan observed that among the 81% segregates of mutually Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, 51 (63%) produced robust biofilm and 30 (37%) produced modest biofilm; in general, Gram-positive bacteria were more likely than Gram-negative bacteria to produce biofilm. Additionally, Ahmed (2013) from Erbil, Iraq, stated that of 118 Gram-positive bacteria, 95 (80 points five percent) produced biofilm by the TCP method, whereas 78 (66 points ten percent) produced biofilm by TM (moderate and strong). Contradict Adilson Oliveira et al. (2010). Meher Rizvi, S. C., Fatima Khan, Indu Shukla, and Tariq Mansoor. 2011; Sharma et al. (title 81).

Figure-2-Silver nanoparticles combined with antibiotics cause *P. aeruginosa* to form antibiofilms.

(Figure-3) Silver nanoparticles combined with antibiotics cause *S. aureus* to form antibiofilms.

The results of optical density readings of bacterial culture showed that the presence of nanoparticles with antibiotics inhibited the growth of these bacterial isolates and thus inhibited their ability to form biofilm with the presence of antibiotics The selected antibiotics showed best compatibility with the Ag-NPs on the

biofilm inhibition (21). The results of TCP method by using Ag-NPs with antibiotics were effective than antibiotics alone (22).

Conflict of Interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

Ethical deliberation: The principled commission appropriate the training at Al-Qadisiyah University.

Conclusion

Ag-NPs combined with antibiotics produced better results from the TCP manner than did antibiotics only. The findings of the optical density measurements of the bacterial culture demonstrated that the antibiotic-containing nanoparticles prevented the growth of the bacterial isolates, which in turn prevented the bacteria from being able to form biofilms. On the biofilm inhibition, the chosen antibiotics displayed the best compatibility with the Ag-NPs. Consequently, Gurunathan et al. (2014) suggest that blending Ag-NPs at reduced concentrations with various antibiotics may prove to be a successful anti-biofilm and antibacterial therapy.

Conflict of Interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

Ethical deliberation: The principled commission appropriate the training at Al-Qadisiyah University.

References

1. Staphylococcus aureus interaction with Pseudomonas aeruginosa biofilm enhances tobramycin resistance **NPJ Biofilms Microbiomes, 3 (2017), pp. 1-8**
2. Wu H, Moser C, Wang H-Z, Høiby N, Song Z-J. 2015. Strategies for combating bacterial biofilm infections. *Int J Oral Sci* 7:1–7.
3. Sollid JUE, Furberg AS, Hanssen AM, et al. *Staphylococcus aureus*: determinants of human carriage. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2014;21:531–541
4. Brown, A. N., Smith, K., Samuels, T. A., Lu, J., Obare, S. O., and Scott, M. E. (2012). Nanoparticles functionalized with ampicillin destroy multiple-antibiotic-resistant isolates of Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Enterobacter aerogenes and methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 78, 2768–2774. doi: 10.1128/aem.06513-11
5. Pinheiro L, Brito CI, Pereira VC, Oliveira A, Camargo CH, Cunha Mde L. Reduced susceptibility to vancomycin and biofilm formation in methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus epidermidis isolated from blood cultures. *Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz.* (2014);109(7):871–878
6. Franklin MJ, Chang C, Akiyama T, Bothner B. New technologies for studying biofilms. *Microbiol Spectr.* 2015;3(4)
7. Lewis K. (2010). Riddle of biofilm resistance, *Antimicrob. Agents chemother.*,45:999-1007
8. **Sudhakar,T.; Nanda,A.; George,S.; Janani,B.S.; Evans, M.D.; Markose, T.K.(2014).**Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles from Edible Mushroom and Its Antimicrobial Activity against Human Pathogens. Sathyabama University, Jeppiaar nagar, Rajiv Gandhi Salai Int. J. Pharm.Tech Research CODEN. USA. 6(5) :1718-1723
9. Vestergaard M., Frees D., Ingmer H. Antibiotic Resistance and the MRSA Problem. *Microbiol. Spectr.* 2019;7:18. doi: 10.1128/microbiolspec.GPP3-0057-2018
10. **Karwa A, Gaikwar S, Rai, M.(2011).** Mycosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using Lingzhi or Reishi medicinal mushroom, Ganoderma lucidum (W. Curt.:Fr.) P. Karst. and their role as antimicrobials and antibiotic activity enhancers, *International J.Med. Mushroom.* 13(5): 483- 491.

11. **Banu A., Vandana Rathod, E. Ranganath (2011).** Silver nanoparticle production by *Rhizopus stolonifer* and its antibacterial activity against extended spectrum β -lactamase producing (ESBL) strains of Enterobacteriaceae. *Materials Research Bulletin*.46(9):1417-1423
12. Kirmusaolu S. MRSA and MSSA: The Mechanism of Methicillin Resistance and the Influence of Methicillin Resistance on Biofilm Phenotype of *Staphylococcus Aureus*. In: Enany S., Crotty Alexander L.E., editors. *The Rise of Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance in Staphylococcus aureus*. InTech; Hong Kong, China: 2017.
13. **CLSI (2016).** Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing; 24th Informational Supplement M100-S26. Wayne, PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute
14. Narasimha,G.;Praveen,B.;Mallikarjuna.K.;Raju.B.B.D.:(2011) Mushrooms(*Agaricusbisporus*) mediated biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles, characterization and their antimicrob. Activity *Int. J. Nano Dim.* 2(1): 29-36, Summer.
15. Bose, D., and Chatterjee, S. (2016). Biogenic synthesis of silver nanoparticles using guava (*Psidium guajava*) leaf extract and its antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Appl. Nanosci.* 6, 895–901. doi: 10.1007/s13204-015-0496-5
16. Pramodhini, S.; Niveditha, S.; Umadevi, S.; Kumar, S.; and Stephen, S. (2012). Antibiotic resistance pattern of biofilm-forming uropathogens isolated from catheterized patients in Pondicherry, India. *Australasian Medical Journal*,5 (7): 344-348.
17. Hwang, I., HwangJ.H., Choi,H.; Kim,K. and Lee,D.G.(2012) Synergistic effects between silver nanoparticles and antibiotics and the mechanisms involved *J. Med. Microbiol.* 61: 1719–1726.
18. Christensen, G. D., Simpson, W. A., Younger, J. J., Baddour, L. M.,Barrett, F. F., Melton, D. M. & Beachey, E. H. (1985). Adherence of coagulase-negative staphylococci to plastic tissue culture plates: a quantitative model for the adherence of staphylococci to medical devices. *J. Clin. Microbiol* 22:996–1006.
19. Wei G.X., Campagna A.N., Bobek L.A.(2006). Effect of MUC7 peptides on the growth of bacteria and on *Streptococcus mutans* biofilm. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 57(6):1100–9.
20. Haq, M.U., Rathod,V., Singh,D., Singh,A.K, Ninganagouda,S., and Hiremath,J., (2015).Dried Mushroom *Agaricus bisporus* mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles from Bandipora District (Jammu and Kashmir) and their efficacy against Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains. *Gulbarga University Kalaburagi, Karnataka, Int.J.5(1):1-8.*
21. Nithya R and Ragunathan R (2009). Synthesis of silver nanoparticle using *Pleurotus Sajor Caju* and its antimicrobial activity. *Digest Journal of Nanomaterials and Biostructures* 4 623-629.
22. Panáček,A., Smékalová,M., Kilianová,M., Pruček, P., Bogdanová,K., Večěřová, R., Havrdová, K.,M., (2016)Strong and Nonspecific Synergistic Antibacterial Efficiency of Antibiotics Combined with Silver Nanoparticles at Very Low Concentrations Showing No Cytotoxic Effect;, 21, 26; doi:10.3390/molecules21010026.
23. Ahmed S S., (2013).Microbiological Study of Multi-Drug Resistant Pathogens Isolated From Women With Genital Tract Infection in Erbil. MSc thesis. College of Medicine. Medical University of Hawler. Erbil (Iraq).